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Understanding the Sahel Crisis: An Environmental Approach

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ABSTRACT

The Sahel region has faced various conflicts for many years and has defied several peacekeeping strategies. Since 2012, the crisis continues to cost the lives of many and destroy valuable property in the region. Between 2012 and 2019, the region, comprising Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger has experienced 1,463 armed clashes, with 4,723 civilians killed at the hands of 195 violent armed groups in 1,263 separate locations, most of whom were civilians. This article employs the Human Needs Theory as the framework for understanding the issue, helps to explain why people behave in certain ways when their needs are not available. This theory assumes that all humans have certain basic universal needs and when these are not met conflict is likely to occur. With this theoretical lens, the article seeks to examine the environmental factors of human needs and how they propel the crisis in the region. The research found that environmental need and the crisis are positively related. Thus, the more the environmental needs are not met, the more difficult it is to end the crisis.

Keywords

Sahel region, Sahel crisis, Environment, Climate change, Desertification, Drought and Flood.

Introduction

For several years, the Sahel region has been challenged by recurring conflicts in almost every country in the region causing thousands of deaths because of food insecurity, violence, terrorism attacks and armed clashes. The victims are civilians and the number of these victims has been increasing dramatically every year. Between 2018- 2019 there was an increase of 7000% in Burkina Faso, 500% in Niger, and 300%

in Mali.¹ While the loss of life and destruction of property is the most visible manifestation of the crisis, its facets go deeper and are more far-reaching. Notably, the crisis correlates with the growing environmental challenges of the area.

The environmental stress is real and constitutes a major form of crisis in the Sahel region. Environmental issues are complex, and multidisciplinary, including climate change, global warming, deforestation, desertification, biodiversity, pollution, droughts, floods, etc. This study seeks to understand the ongoing crisis in the region from such environmental perspectives. The Sahel region suffers greatly from the environmental needs because its population are predominantly agro-based. The need for arable land and water resources that are essential for agro-pastoral livelihoods that dominate the economy in much of the area creates much tension. Indeed, two out of three Sahelians depend on agriculture and livestock. Only for livestock, around 50 million people in the Sahel region depend on this pillar as their livelihood.² The Sahel region has always been an environmentally challenging territory. During the last decades, the problems have become more pressing. Since the early 1970s, the Sahel in West Africa has suffered from the effects and impacts of climatic conditions through drought, flooding, and desertification. Changes seen in major lakes and rivers of the region provide ample evidence: Lake Chad by 90%, the Gambia, Niger, and Senegal Rivers – shrinking ranges from 25% to 60%.³ In recent years, climate change has exacerbated these long-term environmental vulnerabilities.

This paper discusses how the crisis correlates with the rising environmental needs in the region. Specifically, it explores the various environmental conditions which influence the ongoing crisis and, thereby, seeks to offer insights to the understanding of the situation of the Sahel region and its intertwined environmental and security needs.

Background

Geographically, Sahel is the vast region between sub-Sahara and the Sahara Desert. It comprises Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Gambia, Guinea, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, and Chad. Around 150 million people are living in the region.⁴ According to the UN, Sahel is one of the richest regions in the world in terms of natural resources such as oil, gold, and uranium. Approximately 50 million people live in this region with more than 65% of this population living in rural areas.⁵ They practice agriculture and animal

¹ Burkina Faso. *Press release: political violence skyrockets in the Sahel according to latest ACLED data.* (2019).

https://acleddata.com/acleddatanew/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/ACLED_Sahel-Press-Release_3.2019.pdf

² Erik Alda. *Rising Tempers, Rising Temperatures.* (Washington D.C.: The World Bank 2014).

<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/23838/Rising0tempers00in0the0Sahel0Region.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

³ Kamuanga Mulumba JB, et al. *Livestock and regional market in the Sahel and West Africa: Potentials and Challenges.* (Paris: SWAC-OECD/ECOWAS 2008). <https://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search.do?recordID=QM2008000139>

⁴ Ahmet Çonkar. *Development And Security Challenges in the Sahel Region.* Report. Mediterranean and Middle East Special Group (GSM). Nato Parliamentary Assembly (2020): 2020.

⁵ Anonymous, “La situation démographique du Sahel: deux fois plus d’habitants en l’an 2015,” [The demographic situation in the Sahel: two times more inhabitants in the year 2015]. *Pop Sahel.* July (1992): 8-10.

husbandry contributing nearly 35% of the countries' GDP.⁶ In some countries, the percentage is even higher. In Burkina Faso, for example, 82.7% of the population live in rural areas. The national economy is largely based on agriculture, livestock, and forestry. The agricultural sector alone employs more than 90% of the population, with a contribution of 40% to the GDP.⁷

The economic development of the Sahel is mostly dependent on crop farming and livestock, primary production, which, in turn, “is dependent upon the seasonal distribution of precipitation and its annual variation even more than the annual, global amount of rainwater.”⁸ In Burkina Faso, Chad, Mali, and Niger, herders contribute between 10 and 15% of the GDP in these countries.⁹ Particularly in Chad, pastoralism represents 80% of the national livestock sector.¹⁰

Poor environmental conditions diminish already limited natural resources. In recent years, long-standing environmental problems have deteriorated further because of climate change. Since the late 1970s, the region has been affected by climatic constraints such as multiple droughts on one hand (the case of valleys of the Senegal and Niger rivers, oases), and flooding on the other hand, resulting in recurrent famines. If the two main activities in the region—crop farming and livestock—are hampered, it creates economic problems including unemployment, economic hardship, and less productivity. In 2014, the European Parliament reported that in Mali every year, about 300,000 youths who enter the labor market are unable to find employment; leading to a surge in poverty levels.¹¹ This has been an issue of concern because of the youth of the population of the area. For instance, people aged between 15 and 40 years constitute a substantial 70% of Mali's population of 14 million.¹² Such vulnerable conditions of the youth clearly jeopardize the peace and stability of the region, spurring instability and violent uprisings.

Literature

Some scholars argue that climate change is the cause of all other crises. Richard Tol views climate change as “the mother of all externalities: larger, more complex, and more uncertain than any other environmental problem.”¹³ In the same view, Tor A. Benjaminsen observes that conflicts in the Sahel have their origin in

⁶ A. Ben, Mohamed N. Van Duivenbooden, and S. Abdoussallam. “Impact of climate change on agricultural production in the Sahel—Part 1. Methodological approach and case study for millet in Niger.” *Climatic Change* 54.No.3 (2002): 327-348.

⁷ Juliette Tégawendé Nana. “Impact of climate change on cereal production in Burkina Faso.” *Journal of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences*. 8 no.1 (2019): 14-24.

⁸ Claude Raynaut et al., *Societies and Nature in the Sahel*. (New York: Routledge, 1997).

⁹ Rachel Cooper, *Natural Resources Management Strategies in the Sahel*. K4D Helpdesk Report. (Brighton: Institute of Development Studies, 2018).

¹⁰ Kratli Saverio, et al. *Pastoral systems in Dar Sila, Chad: A background paper for Concern Worldwide*. (Boston: Feinstein International Center 2018). https://admin.concern.net/sites/default/files/media/migrated/pastoralist_systems_in_dar_sila_chad.pdf

¹¹ European Parliament, *Mali: Economic Factors Behind the Crisis*, Directorate-General for External Policies, Policy Department Study (2014). http://www.youthpolicy.org/wp-content/uploads/library/2014_EuropeanParliament_ReportPolicy_Mali.pdf

¹² Ismail, W. Olonisakin, F., Picciotto, B. & Wybrow, D. *Youth Vulnerability and Exclusion (YOVEX) in West Africa: Synthesis Report*, Conflict, Security and Development Group (CSDG) Papers, 21. 2009.

¹³ Richard Tol, “The economic effects of climate change.” *Journal of economic perspectives* 23, no. 2 (2009): 29-51.

climate change, which limits natural resources.¹⁴ Similarly, Leif Brottem considers that the climate change create a resource scarcity, this factor generates violent conflicts in the Sahel region. Brottem concludes from the analysis of a collection of “land-use conflicts” from 1992 to 2009 that most of the crises in the Sahel have their roots in the adverse climate change, which limits land resources in the sub-region.¹⁵ This assertion is validated by the obvious fact that each of these cases is in one way or the other linked with some claims for resource ownership. In the same vein, Solidarités International observes that the effects of the floods and droughts have led to the degradation of agro-pastoral activities. For example, in 2019, in Mali and Niger, floods have caused the deterioration and loss of fertility of the land, leading to a fall in agro-productivity.¹⁶ Stephen Harmon has also demonstrated how the environmental crisis has affected the region: the Touareg in northern Mali suffered the destruction of their pastoral economy due to the droughts in the 1970s. He observes that the region experienced about 80 % loss in livestock in that period.¹⁷ This view is shared by analysts working for institutions active in the field. For instance, Marcus Aranju, writing for Climate Institute, underscores the importance of climate change for local conflicts in the Sahel.

More so, Anthony Nyong, a Senior Climate Change Scientists at the International Development Research Center (IDRC) at the Regional Office for Eastern and Southern Africa in Nairobi, Kenya, argues that climate change in the world and precisely in the Sahel is one of the major causes generating divisions and creating conflicts between populations.¹⁸ The incessant desertification of the Sahel region is indeed making the land resource less productive (at least for agricultural purposes). Factions in this region have to compete for the limited land resources, thereby creating conflicts or at least, flaming old conflicts. Other authors have studied specific environmental aspects.

Megan Darby argues that governments’ legitimacy continues to fade as farming and livelihoods suffer at the hands of climate change. Due to this, she posits that Nigeria, Niger, Chad, and Cameroon are “a ripe recruiting ground for Islamic extremism and the illicit trades in drugs, arms and people that sustain it.”¹⁹ In the same vein, Monique Barbut, Former Executive Secretary of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) confirms that the results of climate change can cause conflict.²⁰ According to her, it is no coincidence that the Lake Chad region has been the cradle of Boko Haram and the home of Al-Qaida

¹⁴ Benjaminsen, Tor A., Koffi Alinon, Halvard Buhaug, and Jill Tove Buseth. “Does climate change drive land-use conflicts in the Sahel?” *Journal of peace research* 49, no. 1 (2012): 97-111.

¹⁵ Leif Brottem, “Pastoral Resource Conflict in the Context of Sudano–Sahelian Security Crises: A Critical Review of Research.” *African Security* 13.4 (2020): 380-402.

¹⁶ Solidarités International. Le Sahel au coeur des enjeux du changement climatique. 13 mars 2020 <https://www.solidarites.org/fr/en-direct-du-terrain/le-sahel-au-coeur-des-enjeux-du-changement-climatique/>

¹⁷ Stephen A Harmon. *Terror and insurgency in the Sahara-Sahel region: corruption, contraband, jihad and the Mali war of 2012-2013*. (London: Ashgate Publishing, 2014).

¹⁸ Anthony Nyong. “Climate-related conflicts in West Africa.” *Environmental Change and Security Program Report* 12 (2006): 36.

¹⁹ Megan Darby. *Boko Haram terrorists thriving on climate crisis: report*. Climate Home News, April 20, 2017. <https://www.climatechangenews.com/2017/04/20/boko-haram-terrorists-thriving-climate-crisis-report/>

²⁰ UN Security Council. *Le Représentant spécial affirme que le Sahel doit faire face à la montée de l’insécurité et aux effets des changements climatiques*. –CS/12378, 16 Mai 2013 <https://www.un.org/press/fr/2016/cs12378.doc.htm>

in the Maghreb. The Former Executive Secretary claims that about 41 million unemployed young people continue to live in deplorable, poor, and vulnerable conditions in the Sahel region alone. This further highlights the environmental dimensions of the crisis.

More to that, the repeated floods of 2007, 2008 and 2009 which devastated thousands of fields, caused a significant decline in crop productivity in the Sahel region.²¹ These poor rainfall patterns continue to deprive economic activities, which are mainly agro-based. While most of these scholars show the economic impacts of the environmental needs on humanity, no direct study has focused mainly on the link between these needs and the ongoing crisis in the Sahel. This is the lacuna the paper seeks to fill in literature.

Materials and methods

This work tackles the crisis in the Sahel region from 2012, a deeper understanding of the crises from environmental dimensions, and their impacts on this region. The research uses both qualitative and quantitative methods with the Human Needs Theory as a theoretical Framework.

As can be deduced from the scholars listed in the literature review, the crisis in the region could be explained as deriving from the struggle of people in the area to satisfy their human needs. Human Needs Theory will serve as the theoretical framework within which the research will be conducted.

The Human Needs Theory—although no universal definition exists—holds that “all humans have certain basic universal needs and that when these are not met conflict is likely to occur.”²² Human Need theorists such as Abraham Maslow, John Burton, and Marshall Rosenberg, all propose a set of needs fundamental to humans. Their focus, however, differs from one another. Maslow and Burton focus on human biological, psychological, and social needs but the latter’s work lacks a hierarchical order. Rosenberg’s set of needs has been described as ‘psycho-spiritual in nature,’ including the need for “love integrity,” “celebration and mourning,” and “spiritual communion.” These theorists believe that several consequences could ensue when the means to satisfy these needs are not available.²³ Hossain Banadaki, Danesh describes the Human Need Theory as a valid and useful model to understand some important aspects of human behavior. Thus, this theory was useful in exploring the cycles of environmental, economic, and security crises in the Sahel region. The Human Needs Theory provides the theoretical grounding for both the assumption and the observation that humans react in problematic ways when their basic needs are not met. These needs include environmental life support systems, such as water in needed quantity and a stable climate, as well as an economic basis in income and material living standard. If these needs are not met, people react with

²¹ Center Regional Agrhymet. *Le Sahel face aux changements climatiques. Enjeux pour un développement durable*. Bulletin mensuel/numéro spécial (2010).

²² Hossain Banadaki Danesh. *Human needs theory, conflict, and peace*. In Daniel Christie (ed.), *The encyclopedia of peace psychology*, (Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell, 2011), pre-publication version, https://www.academia.edu/6985348/Human_Needs_Theory_Conflict_and_Peace

²³ John Burton (ed.). *Conflict: Human Needs Theory* (Houndsmill: Macmillan Press, 1995).

problematic behavior including violence, which, in turn, jeopardizes another basic human need for fellow citizens.

According to Christie, Human Needs Theory is a perfect model for understanding “why needs for security and identity are often prepotent in interstate wars and destructive identity conflicts.”²⁴ Therefore, this theory will help explain why environmental, economic and security crises pervade the region. Situating the research in this theory helps understand the needs that propel the three forms of crises identified as pervading the Sahel region. The figure below illustrates how the theory is deployed in this study.

Fig1. Theoretical framework graph from: The Author

²⁴ Daniel J. Christie. "Reducing direct and structural violence: The human needs theory." *Peace and Conflict* 3, no. 4 (1997): 315-332.

Challenge of Climate Change

The Sahelian climate is characterized by a long dry season from October to May and a short wet and rainy season.²⁵ In recent decades, the Sahel region has had an arid and hot climate with a very variable rainfall pattern. According to the IPCC, 2007, temperatures have increased more than 0.5°C since 1979.²⁶ Thereby, the temperature increases 1.5 times faster in the Sahel than in the rest of the world. According to the same source, by 2030 temperatures would continue to increase and could be above 4 degrees Celsius higher.²⁷ The rise in temperature and its variability in the Sahelian zone is recurrent and has adverse effects on agricultural production. For illustration, the synoptic station of Dori and Ouahigouya saw a temperature variation of 34.5 to 37 ° C and 32 to 36 ° C, respectively, for these two stations over the period between 1980 and 2010.²⁸ This can be seen as a result of droughts in Chad.

Since the manifestation of natural (floods, droughts, degraded lands) and man-made threats very frequently over the decades, the effects of climate change could be more disastrous in the Sahel region because most of these states are already exposed to extreme climatic risks.²⁹ Climate change especially affects countries in the Sahel region, which constitute about 20% of the most vulnerable countries in the world, and the least prepared for climate change. In the Sahel, the rainfall precipitation is estimated between 200mm to 600mm per year.³⁰ This rainfall is concentrated in the rainy season which mainly spans from June to October. Climate change limits natural resources like land and water.³¹ In the Sahel region, rain-fed agriculture represents about 93% of cultivated land.³² Therefore, climate change has affected the productivity of crop farmers and herders, bringing economic hardship ultimately resulting in conflicts. As a result of climate change, the region faces continuous floods, droughts, and desertification limiting natural resource availability and creating conflicts among competing farmers and herders (as in the case of Chad).

Climate projections were carried out by the AR4 of the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) on areas particularly sensitive to climate change, such as the Sahel. The results have revealed that the warming will be much higher than the world average in this region, with an increase in temperature of 3 to 4

²⁵ USAID (US Agency for International Development). *Climate Change Risk Profile: West Africa Sahel*. Regional Factsheet.(2017).

²⁶ Alda. *Rising Tempers, Rising Temperatures*. (2014).

²⁷ Christian, Bodewig. *Climate Change in the Sahel: How Can Cash Transfers Help Protect the Poor?*. Brookings Institution (2019). <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/future-development/2019/12/04/climate-change-in-the-sahel-how-can-cash-transfers-help-protect-the-poor/>

²⁸ Lardia Ali Bougma et al. "Perceptions paysannes de l'impact du changement climatique sur le mil dans les zones sahélienne et soudanosahélienne du Burkina Faso." *Afrique Sciences* 14, no.4 (2018): 264-275.

²⁹ Frédéric Bazin, Ali Brahim Bechir, and Djibrine Djimingar Khamis. *Etude prospective: systèmes d'élevage et changements climatiques au Tchad*. (Institut de recherches et d'applications des méthodes de développement, Rapport final, 2013).

³⁰ Martiny Nadège, et al. "Compared regimes of NDVI and rainfall in semi-arid regions of Africa." *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 27.23 (2006): 5201-5223.

³¹ Tor A. Benjaminsen, et al. "Does climate change drive land-use conflicts in the Sahel?" *Journal of Peace Research* 49, no.1 (2012) <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022343311427343>.

³² Benjamin Sultan, Philippe. Roudier, and Seydou. Traore. "Les impacts du changement climatique sur les rendements agricoles en Afrique de l'Ouest." In *Les sociétés rurales face aux changements climatiques et environnementaux en Afrique de l'Ouest*.edited by Sultan Benjamin et al., (Marseille : IRD, 2015): 209-225.

degrees higher than those of the last twenty years of the twentieth century.³³ The Environmental Change Initiative of the University of Notre Dame, Indiana, has developed a Global Adaptation Index, ND-GAIN, which is designed to measure a country's sensitivity and capacity to adapt to the negative impact of climate change. It measures six life-supporting sectors: food, water, health, ecosystem services, human habitat, and infrastructure to show how countries are ready and able to adapt to climate change and its implications. According to its Vulnerability and Readiness Scores, countries in the Sahel, rank between 124th and 182nd positions on the ranking list of the countries in the world made by the Global Adaptation Index, ND-GAIN. This shows that the countries in the Sahel stand little to no chance in adaption and readiness to improve resilience to climate change, three Sahelian countries (Niger, Guinea-Bissau, Chad, and Mali) are among the 10% most at risk.³⁴

Climate change can take various forms. In the Sahel region, desertification, droughts, and floods have been among the most serious. For more than ten years, climate change and many other environmental conditions have created or contributed to the crisis in the Sahel. Considered one of the security threats for more than ten years, climate change has significant effects in Africa and the Sahel region. The Sahel is likely to be socio-economically and politically especially affected by climate change, which is seen as "the" new "security threat: implications for Africa."³⁵ Their factors and their impacts are analyzed in more detail.

Effects of climate change: Degraded lands, Droughts and Floods, Typical case of Desertification: Lake Chad Basin

The Sahel is mostly composed of desert countries: Mali, Chad, and Niger which are suffering from desertification. The Sahelian soil, like almost everywhere in desert countries, is deteriorating because of climate change. This is to say that the land is becoming less fertile as most parts keep losing ground and surface water, rendering them deserts. According to UNEP 2012, land degradation is a major environmental problem affecting the Sahel region in Africa. Lake Chad is a case in point.³⁶

Located in the Sahel, the Lake Chad was considered as one of the largest lakes, the sixth largest in the world, its maximum depth is estimated at 10.5 meters.³⁷ It has an estimated population of 38 million, made up of 70 ethnic groups, mainly dependent on the basin. Lake Chad basin once supplied people living

³³ Met Office Hadley Centre/ Organisation de coopération et de développement économiques (OCDE), Secretariat du club du Sahel et de l'Afrique de l'Ouest. *Climat sahélier perspective et projections*. London : Met Office 2010. <https://www.oecd.org/fr/csao/publications/47093854.pdf>

³⁴ Notre Dame Global Adaptation Initiative (ND-GAIN). *ND-GAIN Country Index*. 2018 <https://gain.nd.edu/our-work/country-index/rankings/>

³⁵ Oli Brown, Anne Hammill, and Robert McLeman. "Climate Change as the 'New' Security Threat: Implications for Africa." *International Affairs* 83, no. 6 (2007): 1141-154. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4541915>.

³⁶ Stephen Doso. "Land degradation and agriculture in the Sahel of Africa: causes, impacts and recommendations." *Journal of Agricultural Science and Applications* 3.03 (2014): 67-73.

³⁷ Michael, Coe T., and Jonathan A. Foley. *Human and natural impacts on the water resources of the Lake Chad basin*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 106.D4 (2001): 3349-3356.

on the borders of Nigeria, Cameroon, Niger, and Chad with fresh water and other resources.³⁸ The drying up of Lake Chad has had an impact on the economy in the Sahel in general and in Chad in particular. In fact, the shrinking of Lake Chad has caused about a 60% drop in fish production in recent years.³⁹ For illustration, in 1966, the production was 140,000 tonnes, in 1980 it reduced by more than 50% to reach 70,000 tonnes and in 2012 production fell by more than 20% to 50,000 tonnes in 2012.⁴⁰ These people are facing resource scarcity, resulting in economic hardship.⁴¹

The figure below shows how Lake Chad has shrunk from 1963 to 2007.

Source: M. Jean Glavany, *La géopolitique de l'eau*, rapport d'information Assemblée Nationale de France, N°: 3000, P:50. <http://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/13/pdf/rap-info/i4070.pdf>

Figure 2: *Lake Chad shrinkage from 1963-2007. Source: FAO⁴²*

The Lake Chad shrunk by 90% which is from 25,000km² to 2,500km² affecting livelihoods that depend the population. It used to occupy significant parts of Niger, Nigeria, Cameroon, and Chad in 1963. By 1973, it had been reduced to a few areas of these countries. As in 1987 and 1997, the lake saw a significant shrinkage. By 2007, it had almost reduced into a minor lake, about 90% of its original size. In 1999, Miller

³⁸ Freedom, C Onuoha. "Environmental Degradation, Livelihood and Conflicts the Implications of the Diminishing Water Resources of Lake Chad for North-Eastern Nigeria." *African Journal of Conflict Resolution* 8, no.2 (2008): 35-61.

³⁹ Patrick Kitoto and Arnold Ombiono. "Réchauffement climatique et migration vers les rives du lac Tchad." *Migrations société* 1 (2016): 149-166.

⁴⁰ Abada Ifanyichukwu and Ajah Anthony Chinonso. *Climate Change And The Political Economy Of Fish Production In The Lake Chad Basin*. Department Of Political Science, University Of Nigeria, Nsukka, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333045561_CLIMATE_CHANGE_AND_THE_POLITICAL_ECONOMY_OF_FISH_PRODUCTION_IN_THE_LAKE_CHAD_BASIN

⁴¹ Oliver Ruppel and Mark B. Funteh. *Climate change, human security and the humanitarian crisis in the Lake Chad Basin region: selected legal and developmental aspects with a special focus on water governance*. (Baden-Baden: Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft, 2019).

⁴²Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. *La crise alimentaire et nutritionnelle du Sahel: L'urgence d'appuyer la resilience des populations vulnérables- Cadre stratégique de réponse régionale Burkina Faso, Gambie, Mali, Mauritanie, Niger, Tchad, et Sénégal*. (Rome: FAO, 2012).

already classified desertification into three categories: light, serious, and severe according to soil productivity. According to him, light desertification is a drop in productivity of 10 to 25%, the serious one is a drop of 25 to 50% and finally, severe desertification is a drop of more than 50% in productivity.⁴³ Given this classification, Lake Chad could be categorized as part of the severe desertification according to its current size.

Yunana et al. affirm that the production of fish, an economic base for the populations living around the Lake is strongly threatened by climate change.⁴⁴ And these problems greatly affect the daily lives of these inhabitants and are likely to affect a significant number of this population in the future.⁴⁵ Today, these populations are confronted with enormous problems among which are famine, poverty, underdevelopment, and also the insecurity characterized by the rise of terrorism (case of attacks from Boko Haram). In the same view, Ms. Monique Barbut, Former Executive Secretary of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification confirms that the results of climate change can cause conflict".⁴⁶ According to her, it is no coincidence that the Lake Chad region has been the cradle of Boko Haram and the home of Al-Qaida in the Maghreb. Aside from her, various experts believe that the results of climate change can contribute to worsening the situation of an existing conflict, as in the cases of Boko Haram and Al-Qaeda in Lake Chad.⁴⁷

Meanwhile, the extent of land degradation in Africa especially in the Sahel region is getting worse. According to the UN, 80% of the Sahel's farmland is degraded.⁴⁸ The severe consequences of drought, floods, desertification or degradation can render the land infertile. Poor rainfall leads to crops failure for farmers depending on rain-fed irrigation, while livestock suffers from scarce drinking water and insufficient pasture. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), some areas of the Sahel are likely to see agricultural yields fall by 20% per decade by the end of the 21st century.⁴⁹

Impact of Droughts

⁴³ Ahmed Abubakar, Samir S. Danhassan, and Musbahu G. Abubakar. *Climate change and the dryland resources of Nigeria*. (Chisinau: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, 2019).

⁴⁴ Abada et al., Climate Change.

⁴⁵ Kabé Abel Daiba, Logténé Youssouf Mopate and Maxime Banoin, "Impact de changement climatique et de l'insécurité dans la partie tchadienne du Lac-Tchad." *Afrique Science* 18.1 (2021): 172-185.

⁴⁶ Conseil de Sécurité de l'ONU. *Le Représentant spécial affirme que le Sahel doit faire face à la montée de l'insécurité et aux effets des changements climatiques*. 16 Mai 2013 <https://www.un.org/press/fr/2016/cs12378.doc.htm>

⁴⁷ Conseil de Sécurité de l'ONU. *Le Représentant spécial affirme que le Sahel doit faire face à la montée de l'insécurité et aux effets des changements climatiques*. 16 Mai 2013 <https://www.un.org/press/fr/2016/cs12378.doc.htm>

⁴⁸ Robert, Muggah, and J. A. Cabrera. "The Sahel is engulfed by violence. Climate change, food insecurity and extremists are largely to blame." *World Economic Forum*, 23 (2019). <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/01/all-the-warning-signs-are-showing-in-the-sahel-we-must-act-now/#:~:text=Climate%20change%20is%20partly%20to%20blame.%20The%20United,growing%20longer%20and%20more%20frequent%2C%20undermining%20food%20production.>

⁴⁹ Geo. Le Sahel au cœur des enjeux du changement climatique. 6 Dec 2019. <https://www.solidarites.org/fr/en-direct-du-terrain/le-sahel-au-coeur-des-enjeux-du-changement-climatique/>

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the USA differentiates between different types of drought: meteorological, agricultural, hydrological, etc. Meteorological drought arises when weather conditions are drier. In contrast, hydrological drought occurs when there is a water deficit over a long period after a meteorological drought. This is different from agricultural drought which happens when crops are affected.⁵⁰

By contrast, the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification defines drought as "a naturally occurring phenomenon that exists when precipitation has been significantly below normal recorded levels, causing serious hydrological imbalances that adversely affect land resource production systems".⁵¹ It constitutes 'a deficit of water relative to normal conditions.'⁵² This could be explained by the abnormal situation of some areas when the place gets drier than before, or when the water limit decreases than the initial border, and this is a natural event that might be avoided or reduce the consequences if human beings work on it. Folger in 2017 defines drought as a natural hazard with potentially significant economic, social, and ecological consequences.⁵³ From these points of view, droughts could be seen as a natural phenomenon characterized by a lack or reduction of water in a very specific area, which can worsen and affect the soil, vegetation, and also humans.

As in many countries, those in the Sahel were also hit by the drought. In terms of breeding, more than 30% of the herd was wiped out between 1970 and 1980.⁵⁴ The drought has become one of the major aspects of the environmental crisis in the Sahel because it has a lot of effects on the population activities and consequently it contributes to the worsening of the crisis. Centre Regional Agrhymet, an agency of the Permanent Inter-state Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel (CILSS) reports that between 1970 and 1980, the region experienced major droughts which had significant impacts on the rural population and therefore on the economy. This drought was the most dramatic with a 30% decrease in rainfall.⁵⁵ Consequently, several major water points in the Sahel such as Niger, Lake Chad, Senegal, The Gambia, and the Volta have significantly shrunk. Between 1971 and 1989 the Niger river (Onitsha) decreased by 30% and the one for Senegal and Gambia, by nearly 60%.⁵⁶

⁵⁰ National Centers for Environmental Information. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Definition of Drought. Undated. <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/monitoring-references/dyk/drought-definition>

⁵¹ Abubakar et al., Climate Change.

⁵² Benjamin Lloyd-Hughes. "The impracticality of a universal drought definition." *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 117, no. 3 (2014): 607-611.

⁵³ D.A. Wilhite, "Drought", in *Encyclopedia of Atmospheric Sciences*, ed. By James Holton, Judith Curry (Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2003) 650-658. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/agricultural-and-biological-sciences/drought>

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Rachel Cooper. *Natural Resources Management Strategies in the Sahel*. (Brighton: Institute of Development Studies, 2018).

⁵⁶ CEDEAO-CSAO/OCDE, "Le Climat et les changements climatiques." *Atlas de l'Integration Regionale en Afrique de l'Ouest*, (2008).. <https://www.oecd.org/fr/csao/publications/40121057.pdf>

From 1982 to 1984, drought severely affected Niger causing an increase in livestock mortality up to 62 percent of the national cattle herd.⁵⁷ The irregular and unequal rainfall in the entire Sahelian zone is a problem. The rainfall has experienced a remarkable decrease in the Sahel with the amount of rainfall that is not the same throughout the region. For example, in the north, the rainfall is lower (100-200 mm a year) than in the south that is recorded around (500-600 mm a year) annually.⁵⁸ Also, in Senegal, a study was carried out over the period from 1921 to 2014, i.e. 94 years, to determine the amount of rain and the rainfall inequality. The results showed that the first part of this period from 1921 to 1967 received an average of 803.2 mm and was characterized by humidity. The second half from 1968 to 2014, was different and was characterized by drought. During this period the rainfall experienced a decrease with an average of 613.8 mm.⁵⁹

In Maïné Soroa in Niger, the average rainfall varies from one period to another. Between 1950 and 1967 the average rainfall was wetter and was estimated at 441 mm per year. On the other hand between 1968 and 1999, it was rather dry and estimated at 330 mm/year. Then from 2000 to 2005, it increased a little more to 361 mm/year which was semi-arid.⁶⁰ All this shows the instability of rainfall due to climate change in the Sahel. In the past, in sub-Saharan Africa and particularly in Niger, the first rains began in the 7th month of the agricultural year and lasted for 4 to 5 months, nowadays the rain falls late around the 8th and 9th months resulting in a reduction in the amount of rain but also the length of the rainy season. It is reduced to 3 or rarely 4 months.⁶¹ This does not only delay the launch of fieldwork but also affects the quality of the products and their yield.

This has serious consequences for regional food security, because, at least 95% of the food production in the Sahel region is based on rain-fed agriculture.⁶² Sometimes, the problem is not lack of water but too much of it.

Impact of Floods

The term, “flood” could be defined as a “Period when tide level is rising; often taken to mean the flood current which occurs during this period.”⁶³ A flood is an overflow of a considerable amount of water beyond its normal limits; it could be on dry land as well as on a river, stream, lake, ocean, etc. Floods are

⁵⁷ W. Al., G. Orking, and O. Clima. *Climate change and food security: a framework document*. (Rome: FAO, 2008).

⁵⁸ Cooper. *Natural Resources*.

⁵⁹ Pascal Sagna, Ousmane Ndiaye, Cheikh Diop, Aïda Diongue Niang et Pierre Corneille Sambou. “Les variations récentes du climat constatées au Sénégal sont-elles en phase avec les descriptions données par les scénarios du GIEC ?” *Pollution Atmosphérique*, 227 (2015). <http://odel.irevues.inist.fr/pollutionatmosphérique/index.php?id=5320>

⁶⁰ B. Dieppois, *Relations Entre La Pluviométrie Au Sahel Central Et Divers Indices Climatiques Sur L’atlantique: Exemple De La Station De Maïne-Soroa (Se Niger) Entre 1950 Et 2005*. 23ième Colloque De L’association Internationale De Climatologie, Rennes. 2010.

⁶¹ Benjamin, Sultan, et al., eds. *Les sociétés rurales face aux changements climatiques et environnementaux en Afrique de l’Ouest*. IRD éditions, 2017.

⁶² MrGeogWagg. *Climate Change and the Sahel Region*. <https://mrgeogwagg.wordpress.com/2015/10/05/climate-change-and-the-sahel-region/>

⁶³ Reinhard, Flick E., et al. “Flooding” versus “inundation.” *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union* 93.38 (2012): 365-366. <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1029/2012EO380009>

one of the natural disasters affecting the Sahel region. Since the second half of the 20th century the Sahel, like many other regions, has been affected by 20 to 30% reduction in precipitation according to Batterbury and Warren, 2001.⁶⁴ The rainfall in the Sahel breaks down and causes crucial effects on this region. According to Maranz, between 1966 and 2000, Sahel recorded about 100mm of rainfall per year.⁶⁵ For MrGeogWagg, at least 95% of the food production in the Sahel region is based on rain-fed agriculture.⁶⁶

The poor rainfall patterns continue to deprive economic activities, which are mainly agro-based. The rainfall is not equal throughout the region, in some parts the amount of rainfall is reasonable sometimes, in others less, not to say insufficient. While certain parts of the region experience reduced rainfall other parts received a high amount of rain resulting in floods. In 2003, floods caused enormous material, crop, and human loss to several of the Sahel including Burkina Faso, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, and Senegal.⁶⁷ The repeated floods of 2007, 2008, and 2009 which devastated thousands of fields, caused a significant decline in crop productivity in the Sahel region. In 2009, in five countries including two of the G5 Sahel (Burkina Faso and Niger) about 600,000 people were affected by the floods.⁶⁸ The heavy rains had significant impacts in the south of Mauritania and the north of Senegal as in many countries, particularly those of the Sahel. In terms of breeding, more than 50,000 head of cattle and 50,000 small ruminants have been killed by these disasters.⁶⁹ The consequences of the floods in Senegal were enormous. In 2012, Senegal recorded groundnut and millet harvests between 923 and 720 kg/ha. Two years later, in 2014, yields were down between 673 and 513 kg/ha. Between the two years, yields fell by 27-29%.⁷⁰ Floods have destroyed houses, schools, health establishments, places of worship, roads, and public places. Between 1998 and 2020 Niger was severely hit by repetitive and continual flooding which caused material damage and also human damage especially in the regions of Tillabéry and Dosso. A total of 3,115,290 people have been affected, more than 225,000 houses destroyed, losses of 205,000 hectares of crops, and 7,100 localities estimated to be affected by floods. This corresponded to between 23% and 18% of people were affected, 24% and 22% of localities were affected, 16% and 20% of houses destroyed, and finally between 57% and 18% of the crops were affected.⁷¹

As another case in point, the city of Maroua in Cameroon has experienced unstable periods due to climatic conditions such as drought but humidity and flooding since 1992. Since 2012, floods have had major

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ Terence Epule Epule, et al. "Climate change adaptation in the Sahel." *Environmental Science & Policy* 75 (2017): 121-137. https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/169214/3/ESP_TXT.pdf

⁶⁶ MrGeogWagg. *Climate Change and the Sahel Region*. 2015 <https://mrgeogwagg.wordpress.com/2015/10/05/climate-change-and-the-sahel-region/>

⁶⁷ Nouaceur Zeineddine, Imen Turki, and Benoît Laignel. "Changements climatiques au Sahel: des conditions plus humides et plus chaudes en Mauritanie." *Sécheresse* 24.2 (2013): 85-95.

⁶⁸ François Gemenne et al. "Changement climatique, catastrophes naturelles et déplacements de populations en Afrique de l'Ouest." *Geo-Eco-Trop: Revue Internationale de Géologie, de Géographie et d'Écologie Tropicales* 41.3 (2017) : 317-337.

⁶⁹ Ibid

⁷⁰ Pascal, Sagna et al. "Les variations récentes du climat constatées au Sénégal sont-elles en phase avec les descriptions données par les scénarios du GIEC?" *Pollution Atmosphérique* 5320 /1970).

⁷¹ Vieri Tarchiani, et al. "Les Inondations au Niger 1998-2020." ANADIA 2.0. Climate change adaptation. Report No27 (2021). July 2021. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.33927.52645](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33927.52645)

consequences on agricultural production in Cameroon. Six departments have been affected; Kai-Kai, the most affected locality by floods in this region recorded a loss of 12,000 hectares of rice, 13,308 hectares of Sorghum, 292,662 hectares of millet, 2, 330 hectares of cowpea.⁷² In 2012, 255,000 hectares on which wheat and other cereal was sown were flooded, 100,000 households agricultural affected, and 161,562 hectares of crops were totally destroyed. Either a cereal deficit estimated at 455,000 tonnes, or 30% of national needs according to the Chad / FAO Emergency Profile (2012).⁷³

Connection between Climate Change and the Crisis

Climate change has had an impact on agriculture and logically on agricultural production, which has created food insecurity in the Sahel region. Several countries in sub-Saharan Africa have seen animal production be affected by climate change in general and particularly severe droughts of recent decades. According to MrGeogWagg, around 18 million people in the region were at risk in 2012 for lack of food as there was a food crisis due to the effects of climate change.⁷⁴ In the Sahel region, in 2012, the food crisis was notorious, more than 33 million people were classified as food insecure, according to the World Economic Forum 2018. In 2015, food-insecure people were estimated to be 410,000, nearly 2 million in 2014.⁷⁵ In Burkina Faso alone had registered more than 330,000 people who were facing food insecurity due to the climate that limited the natural resources, cause the rise of the food price. The prove is the global food price index rose by 9 percent; and one year later by 37 percent, conferring FAO in 2006.⁷⁶ Especially in Africa, the food prices increased by 46.5% as a result of the adverse effects of the floods between 2007 and 2008.⁷⁷ Burkina Faso, like other Sahelian countries, is affected by the effects of climate change, specifically in the area of agriculture and animal husbandry. On the agricultural field, the production of millet has suffered losses of up to (62%) and animal husbandry has seen the loss of wild species estimated at (68%).⁷⁸

According to, Burke et al., climate change has impacts on conflicts and civil wars in Africa which have become frequent in recent years. This is to say that Climate change continues to limit land resources in the sub-region, increased “land-use conflicts” witnessed in the region over the years. As an illustration, in

⁷² Samuel Abossolo Aimé, et al. "Dynamique pluviométrique et son incidence sur la production du maïs à Dimako, Région de l'Est du Cameroun." In *Perturbations climatiques et pratiques agricoles dans les zones agroécologiques du Cameroun*, edited by Samuel Aimé Abossolo, Joseph Armathé Amougou and Mesmin Tchindjang (Saint-Denis : Connaissance et savoir, 2017), 139-154.

⁷³ Oxfam, 'Evaluation of Oxfam's Humanitarian Response in Chad Project. Effectiveness Review' <https://oxfamlibrary.openrepository.com/bitstream/handle/10546/313059/er-food-crisis-chad-effectiveness-review-260214-en.pdf?sequence=3> 26 Feb 2014.

⁷⁴ "Climate Change and the Sahel Region." MrGeogWagg October 20, 2015 <https://mrgeogwagg.wordpress.com/2015/10/05/climate-change-and-the-sahel-region/>

⁷⁵ Mamadou Camara et al., "Effet de la crise au Sahel sur la sécurité alimentaire: cas du Mali," *Revue des Etudes Multidisciplinaires en Sciences Economiques et Sociales*, No 6.1. (2021) . DOI <https://doi.org/10.48375/IMIST.PRSM/remses-v6i1.24471>

⁷⁶ Ibid

⁷⁷ UNECA, *Economic Report on Africa 2009 : Developing African Agriculture Through Regional Value Chains*, (Addis Ababa: UNECA, 2009).

⁷⁸ Ibid

Burkina Faso, there were 4,000 farmer-pastoralist conflicts between the periods from 2005 to 2011.⁷⁹ And these conflicts occurred because the herders moved more and more towards fertile land either to water their cattle or in search of crop residues. It is clear that they clash with farmers when the cattle are deliberately or through awkwardness directed to devastate the farmers' fields, the farmers retaliate and this is how conflicts are generated.

The drought has negatively impacted the agriculture and pastoral productivity. In 1976, amid a drought, Senegal recorded up to 40% of the unemployed, all under 25 years of age. Four years later, unemployment reached 65% of unemployed in Mauritania for an age group of 15 to 24 years.⁸⁰ All these make the land less fertile and therefore less productive. What limits the natural resources; affecting the food output, affects the activities of the population because today it is not everyone who can go about their regular occupations. Besides, the food security of a large part of the Sahelian population depends on the cultivation of food grains (especially millet or sorghum).⁸¹ Because the land is simply degraded less productive for agriculture, the animals can no longer cut and graze the grasses as in the past (case of the Fulani deprived of their sylvo-pastoral activities in central Ferlo). The number of people facing food insecurity as a result of climate change in the Sahelian countries is significant, there are represented respectively: Niger 787.006, Burkina Faso 741.848, Mauritania 623.981, Chad 387.333, and Mali 350.600.⁸²

Burkina Faso, approximately 1.1 million people are internally displaced by violence and conflicts linked to the environment.⁸³ Between 2015 and 2020, there was an increase of major flooding up to 180%, which caused food insecurity to rise to 76% between 2019 and 2021.

Findings and Discussion

The study found that the security issues overlap with the environmental needs in the Sahel region.⁸⁴ The crisis in the Sahel, resulting mainly from the vagaries of the weather, affects the Sahelian population and the region's development. Repetitive droughts have contributed to the reduction of pastoral resources in West Africa, this scourge has forced a large number of pastoralists to move with their cattle to wet and fertile areas to water and feed. According to FAO (2011a), and Diop (2012), several organizations indicate that each year more than 2,000,000 cattle are involved in transhumance in Benin, Nigeria, Mali, and Burkina

⁷⁹A. M Tokede, et al. "Impact of pastoralists-farmers' conflicts on agroforestry farmers' Psychology and agricultural production in north central Nigeria," *Global Journal of Agricultural Sciences* No 20.1 (2021): 1-9.

⁸⁰ De Lutte, Comité Permanent Inter-Etats. *Contre la Sécheresse dans le Sahel (CILSS). Institut du Sahel. Programme majeur population/développement (CERPOD). Rapport de recherche.* Ministère de l'Economie et des Finances. Direction de la Prévision et de la Statistique (DPS). Profil démographique et socio-économique du Sénégal 2000 (1960): 174.

⁸¹ Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) ; International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (Icrisat). *L'économie mondiale du sorgho et du mil : faits, tendances et perspectives.* (Rome: FAO, 1997).

⁸² Robert "The Sahel" Vol. 23

⁸³ World Food Program USA. *You Should Know About What's Happening in the Sahel and Why It's Spiraling Out of Control.* May 18, 2021 <https://www.wfpusa.org/articles/a-snapshot-of-life-in-the-african-sahel/>

⁸⁴ Daniel Eizenga, "Long term trends across security and development in the Sahel," *West African Papers* No 25 (September 2019) Pages 30

Faso.⁸⁵ And during these movements, there are conflicts, tensions, and violent clashes between the natives and the transhumant foreigners (herders) resulting in the loss of human lives and impact on the economy because most of these cattle who transhumance do not do so not all legally, which is, therefore, a loss for the state. In fact, herders are mobile people who move from point A to point B in search of water wells and grasses to cut down and feed their herds during the dry season or during the drought. During their movement, they have used transhumance. By definition, transhumance is a “system of animal production characterized by seasonal movements of a cyclical nature and to varying extents. These movements take place between complementary ecological zones, under the care of a few people, with most of the group remaining sedentary.”⁸⁶

Environmental issues have become more important because they affect the lives of people and their goods (cattle) living in the affected area while climate change has negative impacts on several countries of the region. . This situation maintains endemic poverty, underdevelopment which send many young people to unemployment, making them vulnerable to several evils including generalized crime and violence gradually repeated causing hundreds and millions of deaths, in 2016 there were 320 deaths, 949 deaths in 2017 and 1,686 deaths in 2018.⁸⁷ The impact of climate change on livestock is a reality, precisely the increase in temperature and drought have a visible impact on this sector in general in the sense that there will be less productivity but also a major impact on the life of animals. When temperatures are higher it contributes to decreased milk production, fertility, fitness, and longevity, while drought could reduce calving rates from 60 to 70 percent to 25 to 30 percent.⁸⁸

Conclusion

Despite the great naturel resources and the development potential, that the Sahel region faces an unprecedented environmental crisis. The results of climate change such as drought, floods, and desertification constitute several threats to human security. Climate change has impacts on the health of the population as each year the number of malnourished children increases due to limited livelihoods. It is an obstacle to food security, water supply, as well as good health. The increase in temperature, the variation in precipitation, and the more intense repetitive drought have had effects on agricultural production and accelerated the process of desertification, the case of the Lake Chad Basin shows how the results of environmental crisis or bad conditions could translate into a complex situation of instability and conflict. This has reduced the means of subsistence of the populations, making them vulnerable and exposed to social instability. Some are obliged to leave their home environment to become migrants in other areas, and the

⁸⁵ Baldomero Molina-Flores, Pablo Manzano-Baena, and Mamadou D. Coulibaly. *The role of livestock in food security, poverty reduction and wealth creation in West Africa*. (Rome: FAO, 2020).

⁸⁶ Ibid

⁸⁷ Evariste Somda. “Enjeux de sécurité au Sahara-Sahel Insécurité au Sahara-Sahel: Enjeux politiques, économiques ou religieux?”. (Mémoire de Master, Université catholique de Louvain, 2019).

⁸⁸ USAID (US Agency for International Development). *Climate Change Risk Profile: West Africa Sahel*. Regional Factsheet. (2017). https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00MVQB.pdf.

latter clash with the native people because of limited resources. Others are exposed to terrorism because of their vulnerabilities. They can be kidnapped or recruited to join the ranks of terrorist groups.

Assessing the crisis from a confluence of factors besides the environment is essential to understand other dimensions of the crisis. Therefore, it is suggested that future research focus on a combination of factors that impact the crisis.

In view of all of the above, the study suggests some points which are not exhaustive but can help to reduce the extent of the crisis and its deterioration. To save the planet, particularly the Sahel and the humans who live there from the effects of climate change, it is imperative to remedy the rise in temperature due to the greenhouse gas escaping from the Earth's atmosphere to increase the heat. For this, it would be ideal to turn to renewable energies.

Elaborate clear climate change adaptation policies that could strengthen the prevention and resilience capacity of the populations and sensitize the people concern. For example, to respond to floods disaster, planning water storage and irrigation during floods and transferring them at the right time on arid soils. Related droughts reforest desert surfaces by transposing plants from humid areas to arid areas and providing the means for them to grow and then ensure monitoring. Intensify awareness of the fight against the excessive cutting of wood by proposing and financing projects for the production of ecological charcoal, the recycling of plastics and other waste into usable tools (tires used in chairs, water bottles made of skins flower...) because generally when the populations cut the woods it is to transform them into firewood and the manufacture of chairs, beds, and tables.

To avoid conflicts between farmers and herders due to natural resources that are limited by the harmful effects of climate change, it is necessary to create cultural activities that can bring these two communities together so that they accept each other and collaborate. Develop policies that can enable herders to meet their needs and those of their herds, but also to nourish the land. For example, install the stockbreeders on well delimited surfaces in which they can graze their troops properly and move only after harvests of the farmers.

Thus, they will feed on crop residues but at the same time enrich the soil with animal waste for the following years. Encourage the development of livestock breeding; local transformation and marketing of animal products such as skin, milk, oil, meat, etc. Because in many countries in Africa precisely in the Sahel, the population just eat meat and drink milk, but the rest like skin they used to through it. This could be used to make shoes, bags, clothes... And by this way the importance of livestock could be view by the population.

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